

***In Silico* Evolutionary and Structural Analysis of RAB2B Protein in the Context of Migraine**

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Abstract

RAB2B, a member of the Rab GTPase family involved in Golgi-endoplasmic reticulum vesicular trafficking, has been associated with chronic migraine through altered exosomal protein profiles. This study employs *in silico* approaches to investigate the evolutionary conservation of RAB2B and its potential interaction with common migraine therapeutics. Phylogenetic analysis of coding sequences from diverse mammalian species revealed exceptional conservation (bootstrap values 90-100%), supporting its essential cellular function. Molecular docking analysis against the RAB2B crystal structure (PDB: 2A5J) with three non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) showed differential binding affinities: naproxen (-4.37 kcal/mol) and mefenamic acid (-4.21 kcal/mol) exhibited stronger predicted binding than aspirin (-3.18 kcal/mol). These computational findings suggest that RAB2B's structural pocket may differentially interact with migraine therapeutics, providing a preliminary computational framework for exploring the structural relevance of RAB2B in migraine-associated pathways.

Keywords: RAB2B, migraine, phylogenetic analysis, molecular docking, bioinformatics, NSAIDs, GTPase, Neurological disorder

1. Introduction

Migraine is a complex neurological disorder affecting approximately 14% of the global population (Dong *et al.*, 2024), with significant genetic predisposition identified through genome-wide association studies (Bogatova *et al.*, 2025; Grangeon *et al.*, 2023). Among implicated genes, RAB2B (Zhang *et al.*, 2025) encodes a small GTPase involved in regulating vesicular transport between the endoplasmic reticulum and Golgi apparatus. Dysregulation of vesicular trafficking has been proposed as a potential mechanism in migraine pathophysiology, though the specific role of RAB2B remains unclear (Aizawa & Fukuda, 2015).

This self-directed computational study aims to investigate two aspects of RAB2B biology: (1) its evolutionary conservation across mammals, which may indicate functional importance, and (2) its potential structural interactions with commonly used migraine therapeutics (aspirin, naproxen, and mefenamic acid) (Ezzati *et al.*, 2023) through molecular docking analysis.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Sequence Retrieval and Phylogenetic Analysis

RAB2B coding sequences (CDS) were retrieved from NCBI GenBank for representative mammalian species (Accession numbers: XM_054376818, XM_058429405, XM_004054896, XM_003260848, XM_058429402, NM_001163380, XM_006161419, XM_063090559, XM_011382761, XM_060146250, XM_057724968). Multiple sequence alignment was performed using MUSCLE algorithm. Phylogenetic analysis was conducted using MEGA11 software with the Neighbor-Joining method and p-distance model (Morohoshi *et al.*, 2021).

2.2. Molecular Docking

The crystal structure of RAB2B (PDB ID: 2A5J) (Nath *et al.*, 2025) was retrieved from the Protein Data Bank. The receptor was preprocessed with AutoDock version 1.5.7 for docking. Ligand structures for aspirin, naproxen, and mefenamic acid were obtained from PubChem database in 3D SDF file format. Downloaded sdf files were converted to PDB file format using Open Babel 3.1.1. For ligand preparation, ligand files in PDB format were opened through the “ligand” option in Autodock tools and the file was

saved as PDBQT. Molecular docking was performed using AutoDock with a grid box covering the entire protein surface (**center**: $x=28.90725$, $y=0.761375$, $z=27.200125$; **dimensions**: $40 \times 40 \times 40$ Å). The lowest binding energy conformation from each docking run was selected for analysis. Docking results were visualized by Discovery Studio Visualizer 2025 (Rahman & Das, 2021).

3. Results

3.1. Phylogenetic Analysis of the RAB2B

The phylogenetic tree constructed from RAB2B coding sequences shows strong evolutionary conservation across mammalian species (**Fig. 1**). The topology is well-supported with bootstrap values ranging from 90% to 100%. Two major clades are evident:

Clade I (sequences: XM_054376818, XM_058429405, XM_004054896, XM_003260848, XM_058429402, NM_001163380) shows near-zero branch lengths (0.000–0.001), indicating minimal nucleotide divergence among closely related mammals, likely primates.

Clade II (sequences: XM_006161419, XM_063090559, XM_011382761, XM_060146250, XM_057724968) displays slightly greater but still minimal divergence (branch lengths: 0.011–0.033) with 99% bootstrap support, representing more distantly related mammalian lineages.

The exceptionally short branch lengths throughout the tree and high bootstrap values confirm that RAB2B is under strong purifying selection, consistent with its essential role in intracellular trafficking.

Figure 1. *In Silico* Evolutionary Analysis of RAB2B Protein

3.2. Differential Binding of NSAIDs to RAB2B

Molecular docking analysis revealed differential binding affinities of three NSAIDs to the RAB2B structure (**Table 1**). Naproxen showed the strongest predicted binding affinity (-4.37 kcal/mol), followed by mefenamic acid (-4.21 kcal/mol) and aspirin (-3.18 kcal/mol). The estimated inhibition constant (K_i) for naproxen was in the mid-micromolar range (624.66 μ M), while aspirin showed millimolar affinity (4.64 mM). The binding energies were primarily driven by van der Waals, hydrogen bonding, and desolvation contributions (**Fig.2**), (**Fig.3**), (**Fig.4**).

Table 1. Docking Scores, RMSD Values, and Predicted Inhibition Constants (K_i) of NSAIDs with RAB2B protein

Ligands	Binding energy	Cluster RMSD	Inhibition Constant, K_i	Final Intermolecular Energy
Aspirin	-3.18	0	4.64 mM	-4.38 kcal/mol
Naproxen	-4.37	0	624.66 μ M	-5.56 kcal/mol
Mefenamic acid	-4.21	0	818.13 μ M	-5.40 kcal/mol

Figure 2. Predicted binding position of Aspirin in the binding pocket of RAB2B

Figure 3. Predicted binding position of Naproxen in the binding pocket of RAB2B

Figure 4. Predicted binding position of Mefenamic acid in the binding pocket of RAB2B

4. Discussion

This *in silico* analysis provides two key insights into RAB2B biology relevant to migraine:

First, the exceptional evolutionary conservation of RAB2B across mammals, evidenced by minimal nucleotide divergence and high bootstrap support, underscores its fundamental cellular role. Such conservation typically indicates strong functional constraints, suggesting that even minor perturbations in RAB2B function could disrupt vesicular trafficking pathways implicated in migraine pathophysiology.

Second, the differential binding predictions between NSAIDs suggest a potential structural basis for variable therapeutic efficacy. While all three compounds are used in migraine management, naproxen's stronger predicted binding to RAB2B may reflect a potential off-target or indirect interaction beyond its primary cyclooxygenase inhibition (Wilcha *et al.*, 2024). The binding site analysis suggests interactions

with predicted region of RAB2B, possibly affect GTP binding or protein-protein interactions that are essential for its trafficking function.

Limitations: This computational study requires experimental validation. Docking analyses provide static snapshots; molecular dynamics simulations would better assess binding stability. The functional consequences of NSAID binding to RAB2B remain speculative without *in vitro* or cellular assays.

5. Conclusion

This project demonstrates that RAB2B is highly evolutionarily conserved and may structurally interact with migraine therapeutics with differential affinity. Naproxen shows the strongest predicted binding, potentially indicating a novel interaction relevant to its therapeutic effects. These findings provide a computational foundation for further investigation of RAB2B as a potential target in migraine and suggest that structural bioinformatics approaches can generate testable hypotheses for neurological disorder mechanisms.

6. References

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